

Learning by ‘Sprinting’: An Immersive Approach to Raising Awareness of Cancer Genomics for Targeted Therapies

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Purpose. Advancements in cancer genomics have transformed medical practice, emphasizing the need for physicians adept in precision oncology and interdisciplinary collaboration. To address this, we developed "Sprint for Cancer Genomics," a one-day educational initiative to introduce undergraduate students to molecular targeted therapies and collaborative problem-solving within a mock molecular tumor board.

Methods. The 6.5-hour workshop utilized faculty-led didactics, a visual storyboard, an information resource portal, and student leaders to scaffold learning. Participants confronted a *wicked problem*—a meticulously crafted, complex clinical scenario involving colorectal cancer that mirrored real-world dilemmas often encountered. This challenging scenario required students to integrate genomic knowledge and collaborative problem-solving skills to relay information about various clinical decisions for a patient case.

Results. Of the 23 undergraduate participants, 91% were on a pre-medical track. Pre-Sprint, 92% reported low confidence in molecular therapies; post-Sprint, all expressed increased confidence. Students highlighted the workshop's impact on their understanding of medical genomics and its applications. By the end, participants effectively applied their new knowledge and presented high-quality solutions.

Conclusion. The Sprint for Cancer Genomics effectively introduced undergraduates to molecular therapies and interdisciplinary collaboration, preparing them for future challenges in oncology. This model demonstrates the value of dynamic team science in medical education and offers a blueprint for training the next generation of genomically competent physicians.

INTRODUCTION

Despite advancements in cancer diagnosis and treatment, novel therapeutic approaches remain essential to combat this disease. One promising area is molecular targeted therapies, which have shown significant potential in cancers such as breast, lung, and colorectal (Lee et al., 2018). These therapies are increasingly supported by clinical trials and FDA-approved treatments, making them a cornerstone of cancer research. However, their successful implementation requires a shared understanding among clinicians, physicians, and researchers, built through years of training and expertise (Masic et al., 2008).

The effectiveness of molecular therapies also relies heavily on collaboration. Team science, a strategy that harnesses diverse skills and perspectives, is critical to addressing complex scientific challenges. However, implementing team science is inherently complicated and lacks a one-size-fits-all strategy (Hall et al., 2008). For students aspiring to careers in medicine or research, developing collaborative and problem-solving skills early is crucial (Chakraborti et al., 2008). Genomic medicine, as a cross-disciplinary field, exemplifies the need for team science to innovate solutions for pressing healthcare challenges (Roth, 2019).

To prepare undergraduates for the demands of healthcare, innovative strategies are required to cultivate their understanding of complex clinical and scientific domains (Klufas et al., 2020). The *Sprint for Cancer Genomics* exemplifies such innovation by combining educational methodologies with hands-on practical training. The event was designed to introduce pre-medical undergraduates to interdisciplinary challenges, fostering the collaboration and teamwork necessary for success in the dynamic field of team science.

While various undergraduate cancer-related educational programs have been successful, the *Sprint for Cancer Genomics* initiative stands out by integrating research and clinical practice in an innovative and intensive format. Many programs emphasize clinical aspects of cancer, such as patient communication, prevention, and survivorship (King et al., 2023). The Sprint, in contrast, focuses on the intersection of research and clinical practice, particularly through the exploration of molecular tumor boards and collaborative problem-solving mechanisms. Unlike lengthy summer programs (Gaida et al., 2021), the Sprint delivers an intensive, focused experience that emphasizes efficiency, immediate application, and dynamic learning.

By bolstering proficiency in molecular targeted therapy literacy and simulating the complexities of real-world healthcare challenges, the Sprint aimed to prepare students for future roles in healthcare. Student progress was assessed through self-reported confidence levels and the quality of their collaborative projects, providing insights into their growing understanding of clinical genomics and problem-solving skills. This initiative offers a replicable model for engaging students in the critical, collaborative aspects of modern cancer research and treatment.

METHODS

Participant Recruitment

The Sprint for Cancer Genomics event was announced via biosciences email newsletters, distribution lists, and class announcements targeting UT Austin undergraduates interested in medicine, genomics, and research. A QR code linked to a Qualtrics interest form collected information on majors, and interests from 62 respondents. The first 26 respondents were invited to participate, ensuring a focused learning environment.

Curriculum Overview

Pre-Sprint Warm-Up Activities

Participants began the day with team-building activities to create a collaborative atmosphere (**Figure 1**). Warm-up activities included:

- **Video Opportunity:** Students shared their motivations and expectations for the Sprint with a videographer team.
- **Interactive Writing Posters:** Students answered reflective questions on posters, such as “Why do you choose to Sprint for Cancer Genomics?”
- **Storyboards:** Students randomly received patient case “race day bibs” containing information on their team assignment, and case genomic, clinical, and treatment information. Bibs were categorized by color to represent genetic makeup (red for key gene findings; green for variants of unknown significance), biomarkers such as tumor mutation burden and microsatellite status and PD-L1 status (blue), clinical details on diagnosis, stage, age and gender (yellow), and treatments (orange). Additionally, bibs contained information on team assignment (Red, Orange, Green). Students used these bibs to create initial storyboards as a team for the patient case.

The "Wicked" Problem

Students were presented with a complex, interdisciplinary case: a 43-year-old female with stage IV sigmoid cancer, previously treated with FOLFOX, at high risk of recurrence. The problem required students to assume the role of a molecular tumor board member, integrating genomic knowledge, clinical guidelines, and available resources to propose treatment options. Scenarios and frameworks were provided (**Table 1**) to simulate dynamic patient conditions and encourage innovative problem-solving.

Educational Resources

Students received multiple resources to support their learning and casework, including:

1. **Didactic Lectures:**
 - Molecular targeted therapies and biomarkers.
 - Genomic Data Commons Data Portal and public cancer genomics databases.
 - Translational research and its connection to colorectal cancer clinical practice.
2. **Information Resource Portal:**
 - A curated collection of videos, articles, and templates as ‘running playlists’ tailored by faculty and student organizers.
3. **Student Leaders and Ambassadors:**
 - Graduate students led teams, offering expertise and guidance.
 - Undergraduate ambassadors facilitated logistics and communication.

Case Work and Presentations

Following the morning session and lunch, students worked in teams to develop treatment plans supported by evidence. Guided by student leaders, teams synthesized genomic data, explored treatment possibilities, and prepared presentations. Teams presented their findings to an audience of other student teams, researchers, educators, and peers, receiving feedback during a final debrief.

Pre- and Post-Sprint Evaluations

Participants completed a pre-survey to evaluate their baseline knowledge of molecular tumor profiling and identify topics of interest for the Sprint, and additionally, a post-survey immediately after the event to measure changes in knowledge and confidence. A follow-up survey, distributed one week later, captured students’ reflections and key takeaways from the Sprint experience. A test of two proportions was done based on a z-score approximation and implemented using a logit model, assigning statistical significance at $p < 0.05$.

This structured, resource-intensive approach was designed to foster interdisciplinary collaboration and enhance student understanding of molecular targeted therapies and their applications in cancer care. Participants completed a pre-survey to evaluate their baseline knowledge of molecular tumor profiling and identify topics of interest for the Sprint.

RESULTS

Pre-Survey Results

The interest survey generated 62 responses, demonstrating significant interest in the Sprint event. The first 26 respondents were invited to attend. Pre-survey data indicated attendees were primarily from UT Austin's Colleges of Natural Sciences, Engineering, and Liberal Arts, representing over 10 majors, with a majority from the College of Natural Sciences. In terms of academic tracks, 21 students reported being on a pre-medical track, with the remainder pursuing pre-graduate studies (**Figure 2**). Over 67% of attendees reported a preference for traditional lectures as their primary learning method. A low confidence and understanding of molecular tumor profiling and targeted therapies was reported in 92% of participants. Students also reported a strong desire to understand the role of these therapies in cancer treatment.

Post-Survey Results

Of the 23 students who attended the event, significant improvements in confidence and knowledge were reported. Among the students who responded, all reported an above-average confidence in molecular profiling and targeted therapies post-event. No students reported low confidence. A comparison of the proportion of somewhat or very confident versus not confident within pre- versus post- survey was significant for both molecular tumor profiling and molecular targeted therapies (**Table 2**). The students additionally provided detailed, insightful responses in post-event surveys, reflecting newfound competencies. The quality of team presentations further validated these self-assessments. Lastly, students highlighted the inclusive and collaborative nature of the workshop, expressing that the learning environment fostered open dialogue and creativity.

Presentation Results

Students presented their findings in a team-based PowerPoint presentations, showcasing diverse solutions to the "wicked" problem. The red team focused on the patient's specific genetic profile and multiple treatment options (**Figure 3**). The orange team considered population health and demographic factors (**Figure 4**), while the green team explored a single molecular pathway as a treatment focus (**Figure 5**). These presentations demonstrated significant increases in knowledge, creativity, and critical thinking, with teams producing diverse, evidence-based solutions by the end of the event that seemingly reflected their diverse experiences and backgrounds.

Final Survey Results

A week after the event, students reported continued enthusiasm, as indicated by a survey response. Students cited interest in the topic, novelty of the research area, skill development, and collaboration as key reasons for participation. Further, 100% of respondents were "very likely" to recommend the Sprint to their peers.

Summary

In summary, the *Sprint for Cancer Genomics* successfully engaged students in molecular targeted therapies, enhancing confidence and knowledge through a novel, interdisciplinary educational approach. The event's ability to take students with minimal prior knowledge and transform them into informed contributors within hours underscores its effectiveness and potential for replication in other educational contexts.

DISCUSSION

The *Sprint* sets a new standard for educational interventions by combining traditional didactic learning with practical, scenario-based applications, serving as a *crowdsourcing hackathon-style experiential learning initiative* that immerses students in interdisciplinary teamwork and equips them with hands-on problem-solving skills to address real-world challenges in molecular targeted therapies and precision oncology. By utilizing the "wicked" problem framework, the Sprint immersed students in real-world complexities, encouraging immediate application of their knowledge to dynamic and challenging scenarios. This hands-on, interdisciplinary training prepares students for the multi-faceted nature of clinical oncology and collaborative team science. The workshop's emphasis on team-based problem-solving and exposure to molecular tumor boards created an

environment conducive to developing adaptability, critical thinking, and collaboration. These qualities are essential for navigating the rapidly evolving landscape of cancer treatment.

Key Findings and Implications. The Sprint demonstrated significant interest, evidenced by 62 initial applications and the diverse backgrounds of the 26 selected participants. While the majority of students were from UT Austin's College of Natural Sciences and on a pre-medical track, the diversity of majors highlighted the multidisciplinary relevance of the event. This indicates the potential for scaling the workshop to other academic contexts and audiences. Participants reported low confidence levels in molecular tumor profiling and therapies before the Sprint, reinforcing the need for such educational initiatives. Post-surveys revealed statistically significant increases in confidence and knowledge. The surveys also captured strong qualitative feedback, with students highlighting the workshop's effectiveness in improving their understanding of molecular therapies and team dynamics. A notable finding was the variety of preferred learning styles among participants. While traditional lectures were favored, the Sprint's combination of didactics, interactive resources, and team activities catered to different learning preferences, fostering higher engagement and retention. These insights underscore the necessity of diverse instructional methods to meet the needs of varied learners in medical education.

Strengths and Limitations. The workshop's success in achieving confidence and knowledge gains reflects its innovative design and focus on small-group learning. However, limitations included the exclusive participation of UT Austin undergraduate students and potential survey response biases, such as overly positive self-assessments. Additionally, fewer responses to the follow-up survey may have introduced response bias, though the consistent trends in feedback provide strong support for the Sprint's effectiveness.

Future Directions. The overwhelmingly positive response to the Sprint, with 100% of participants indicating they would recommend it to peers, supports its potential as a scalable and recurring educational model. Expanding the initiative to include medical students or other institutions could address gaps in genetic and genomic education identified in existing curricula (Haspel et al., 2021). Furthermore, integrating similar workshops into medical education programs could enhance the genomic literacy and collaborative skills of future healthcare professionals, better preparing them for advancements in cancer treatment.

In conclusion, the *Sprint for Cancer Genomics* exemplifies a forward-thinking, educational innovation, merging research, clinical practice, and team science to address pressing challenges in oncology. This model offers a replicable framework for fostering the next generation of healthcare professionals equipped to drive meaningful advancements in precision medicine.

Acknowledgements

Conception and design JK; Draft AS and JK; participation AC, AS, NB, JK; Draft Editing: AC, AS, NB, JK.

We thank Mrs. Ginger Okoro for the administrative support in coordinating the initiative.

A determination of non-human subjects research was made by the University of Texas at Austin IRB for this study.

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Figure 1: The workflow overview of the Sprint for Cancer Genomics educational event. In order to best facilitate the student’s growth, the event began with a warm up, followed by the introduction to the wicked problem. “Sprinters” were then given dynamic resources to attempt and solve the case study presented to them where they concluded and showcased their findings with student presentations at the end. This framework for the event provided students with an immersive experience focusing on problem solving and teamwork. There were three main warm up activities. The optional Q&A video allowed students to express their thoughts on the sprint's impact and their reasons for attending, providing valuable qualitative insights and factors influencing student engagement. The visual storyboard was a collaborative warm up activity in order to begin organizing the case information and introduce members to one another. This exercise helped randomize groups. The writing opportunity had given students the opportunity to showcase their thoughts to the collective of students and faculty. The information resource portal, designed by the Sprint team, serves as a comprehensive and curated platform for undergraduate students, offering a wide range of valuable information and resources specifically selected to support their needs on the day of the event including the agenda, resources for their presentation, and the playlists. The above figure includes the landing page of the information portal and what information was given to students.

Figure 2: A) The bar chart displays the number of students who had signed-up for sprint and their distribution of majors across common majors. B) The pie chart visually presents the proportion of students interested in Sprint from three main colleges at UT Austin: the College of Natural Sciences, Engineering, and Liberal Arts, highlighting the relative sizes of their interest in the educational opportunity. C) The bar chart depicts the percentage of sprint interested students and their final educational aspirations. D) The bar chart displays the number of students who attended Sprint and completed the final survey and those student’s distribution of year classification.

Figure 3: The Red Team focused on analyzing the individual patient profile, delving into their unique characteristics. Through their comprehensive research, they identified specific genetic alterations and devised targeted treatment approaches. Their insightful presentations not only highlighted potential treatments but also provided a concise and informative summary of their proposed therapeutic strategies.

Figure 4: Taking a broader perspective on the wicked problem, the Orange Team considered various demographic factors such as age, sex, and ethnicity, and their potential implications on the specifics of the patient cases. Their comprehensive approach provided valuable insights into the interplay between demographic considerations and the presented patient profile.

Figure 5: The Green Team pursued a focused approach, centered on exploring a singular pathway and genetic alteration. Their efforts revolved around identifying promising clinical trials that specifically targeted the genetic mutation and pathway under investigation. The Green Team depicted potential avenues for therapeutic advancements, offering a comprehensive understanding of the clinical prospects related to the genetic alteration in question.

Tables

Scenarios		
Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Imaging -	Imaging -	Imaging +
Patient stable with no evidence of disease	Patient has no evidence of disease BUT evidence of tumor markers in blood	Patient progresses with evidence of disease
Marker –	Marker +	Marker -/+

Table 1: Scenarios that the patient could experience as a next step and thus presented to students to add more definition to the wicked problem. Students were asked to consider these scenarios in their decision making in real time to simulate real molecular tumor boards decisions and advancements.

Confidence	Student's confidence of molecular tumor profiling		Student's confidence of molecular targeted therapies	
	Pre-Sprint	Post-Sprint	Pre-Sprint	Post-Sprint
Not Confident	14	0	16	0
Somewhat Confident	10	11	8	13
Very Confident	2	4	2	3

Table 2: The table above presents a comparative analysis of students' self-reported confidence levels in molecular tumor profiling reports and their understanding of molecular targeted therapies before and after participation in the Sprint workshop. It delineates the evolution of confidence levels, showcasing notable enhancements subsequent to the Sprint event.